

A Descriptive Study on Impact of Music on Workplace Productivity

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Madhu, V., and MS Shruthi. “A Descriptive Study on Impact of Music on Workplace Productivity.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 32–38.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575283>

V. Madhu

Assistant Professor, Jain College

MS. Shruthi

Assistant Professor, Jain College

Abstract

Music flows flawlessly through air and touches every soul. It isn't only in the instruments and the voices that the music exists but also in everything else. It's in the whisper of the wind, it's in the myriad raindrops, and it's in the rhythmic beating of the heart as well. Music changes the large world into a small one as it has no boundaries. They say that the sound is the most powerful force in the universe. It has a spiritual aspect to it as well because once the music enters the neural network we have a very limited control on the effects of music as it penetrates the inner most depths of our consciousness.

In this paper an effort is made to study the impact of music in workplace productivity. How often do we see people cruise through routine jobs with music playing in their ears? What we must also consider is that whether it has any impact on the quality of the job because when you are doing multiple things at a time the concentration is bound to get distributed.

And if music has any impact on productivity one should also look at whether it's the ambient music or the music with loud noise that makes people do their job well. We must also consider if there is any part of the music that a worker might find distracting. Another objective of this paper is to see if music works for non-repetitive tasks as well. Another component to a song is lyrics. The tasks which require employee's immersion in it might find songs with lyrics counterproductive. Should music also be familiar to the employee to be able to effectively perform his task or do some people prefer unfamiliar music? This is also another component of this study.

Keywords: Music, Productivity, Motivation, Cognitive tasks, Performance.

Introduction

Music is what people use to escape everyday life, it is known for its ability to reduce stress, removing negative energy, enhancing happiness and so on. Some people make a career out of music and unleash their creativity while some others listen to it when doing everyday chores to make chores a little less boring. According to Nielsen an American market research company an average American listens to music 4.5 hours a day and that number is increasing with every passing year. That number increases when it comes to millennials. It is hard to say when the music was first created but one can see its omnipresence. We probably sang even before we started to speak. Everyone speaks in a different tempo, tone, pitch and even

registers. It is common to see people listening to music when they are at gym or when they are driving or taking a walk but it is also been used by some for tasks such as reading.

It is not news when people say that they listen to music while they are working in their workplaces. Lately employers seem to be fine with their employees escaping into a distraction which has beneficial effects. Here are few facts about music and how it affects our daily life. Firstly when you listen to the music you enjoy the brain releases the neurotransmitter dopamine which makes you feel good. It has also proven to be a substitute to anti- anxiety drugs according to a study conducted on patients who were about to undergo surgery. Secondly lyrics could be counterproductive when it comes to productivity. The more voices you here while performing a task the more you are bound to get distracted. But it’s quite the opposite when it comes to instrumental music (Research from applied acoustics). Thirdly according to a study by sports psychologist Costas Karageorghis physical performance such as workouts or running improves drastically when listening to motivational music by reducing boredom. One can improve the quality of performance as well as increase the duration of exercise. Fourthly in a book called THIS IS YOUR BRAIN ON MUSIC the author Daniel Levitin who is a brain scientists as well as a musician has mentioned how music makes repetitive tasks more pleasurable and increase concentration. Fifthly studies have shown that regions of brain which are responsible for improving concentration are active when you listen to music which is familiar. Sixthly Music affects both introverts and extroverts differently (study published in the Applied Cognitive Psychology Journal). And finally when you listen to music between tasks it could boost productivity according to a study conducted by E. GLENN SCHELLENBERG in his paper Exposure to music and cognitive performance: tests of children and adults.

It all comes down to what type of music one listens to. The productivity or performance depends on how many lyrics are there in the song , familiarity with the song, repetitiveness of the task and also the type of activity whether mental or physical.

It is not to say that this theory applies to everyone. Although music is a universal language it affects different people on different levels. It can be both useful and counterproductive depending upon an individual’s personality. According to Will Tottle, mental health expert and author of the article series Mind Boosting Benefits productivity depends more on individual tendencies rather than musical preference. For example the theory called The Mozart Effect assumes that people who listen to classical music by Mozart become smarter but it since have been proven false as it only makes a person smarter for a short period of time only with respect to temporal and spatial reasoning.

There are some generalizations that you can make even without any research i.e. an average person’s dopamine levels seem to increase when he is listening to music that he is familiar with because he doesn’t have to set aside extra effort to comprehend the beat or any other mechanisms of the song. And also despite individual preferences one can safely assume that an average person would enjoy classical music as it has a soothing effect on the brain which in turn leads to the feeling of joy and calmness which then in turn leads to motivation to perform tasks.

On the other hand there are certain aspects of music which leads to decrease in productivity. Firstly the genre of the music. There is something about this particular aspect of sound called timbre. Not all genres uses the instruments one loves the most at the same time not all genres agree with one’s tastes which uses the instruments one likes. Every instrument has its own timbre to it which awakens one’s inner most feelings or emotions. Some people are into heavy music and some are into soft soothing ones. One need not necessarily be productive when he is listening to music blasting from the next guy’s music player if it is an unfamiliar genre. The second aspect which leads to decrease in productivity is the tempo. Faster tempo might be good for you if you are exercising

but can be an unbearable distraction if your task needs some amount of focus. Slow tempo has also got similar effect. Slow music can make you drowsy and put you off to sleep. Medium or moderate tempo depending upon the individual preferences is what one looks for to get maximum benefits from music. The third one is the lyrics. You would not want someone to constantly talk to when you are working. It's the same with the too much lyrics.

For music to be a beneficial distraction it has to play a background role. It should not demand your brain's analysing powers. The type of music which has a complex song structure can be distracting and can easily cause irritation while performing a task. Most of the music that is popular and stick in peoples' head does not usually have any complex aspects to it be it rhythm or pitch. This is what makes it easier for the brain to memorize it quickly so that one does not need to worry about or even get distracted about where the song is going while performing a task. That does not mean that people who are into complex music cannot simultaneously work and enjoy music.

It's always beneficial for someone who has the habit of listening to music to enhance productivity with music which reduces boredom and creates the illusion of time going fast especially in cases of routine tasks. The reverse is also true i.e. if a person doesn't have this habit then the task is better performed without music or in this case distraction. Even if one has this habit it is not to say that one can ace every task that is given. It depends very much on the difficulty of the task. The more difficult it is, the more concentration and focus and thoughts it demands and hence music can only further distract you. But in case of routine jobs which doesn't require too much thought because of brain's ability to store things in muscle memory, this music listening can be an enhancing experience in terms of productivity. And finally music should be played by your own choice and not be forced upon you which is the case of counter productivity.

Objectives

To Find Out if Music Serves as a Motivation to Perform Tasks

We know that without motivation you would not even get out of the bed every morning. We all need something to live for which makes us fill our hours and days with all that is necessary to take us across the end line. Music is known to change your mood instantly especially when you are bored or fatigued. It is no surprise that people use music to get through a tough workout session or a long commute. Here an effort is made to find that out.

To Find Out if Music has Any Dramatic Effect on Repetitive Tasks

Human brain always needs something new every day. If neurogenesis is to be believed your brain cells in certain regions grow in case of exercise- induced neuroplasticity. That is if you work out regularly, over time you grow new brain cells so you have more space to store new information. But they will soon die if you don't learn anything new. It is almost impossible for brain to stay motivated if it doesn't get new challenges. Just the thought of routine repetitive tasks can make one feel drowsy. But there are certain such tasks an employee cannot avoid when it comes to work. This paper makes an effort in knowing whether music stops the brain from being discouraged to do such tasks.

To Find Out if Music Works for Intense Tasks Which Demands a Lot of Focus?

No matter how hard a task is through repetition it gets stored in your muscle memory and that tough task becomes your second nature where you don't have to put in much brains at all. In that case music can work well despite the task's demand of focus. Here an effort is made to find out if that works for a task which has new challenges.

To Find Out if Music has Any Effect When It is Imposed on Employees

When we choose to listen to music we know we are definitely going to enjoy it. But what if the music is played out loud by someone and you happen to just sit beside that someone? Would that still lead to enhanced productivity or would it have adverse effect on your work? Since it is not the same as listening to music on your headphones voluntarily, an effort is made to get a clear picture on that.

To Find Out if Complex Music Leads to Counterproductive Results

Complexity in music is defined by the songs irregular rhythmic structures, the beat as well as the pitch. An average listener may only like what is easy on his ears. If you throw in complexities that are mentioned above he may find it off putting. Once you add too much lyrics into the song it may make the process even worse. An effort is made to find out complexity’s role in productivity

Review of Literature

Effects of noise and music on human and task performance: A systematic review by Brian H. Dalton and David G. Behm reveals that the effects of music on task performance can be equivocal i.e. Music may facilitate performance involving high levels of concentration and attention. Conversely, music has also been shown to be as distracting as noise during comprehension tasks. Another finding in this study is the tempo of the music. It states that the faster tempo in music helps one to perform tasks faster but could also lead to mistakes. Music can increase irritability in frustrating situations.

And finally according to this paper driving related tasks are hugely influenced by music. Driver stress, anxiety, speed and relaxation are few of the factors that are influenced by music. The results again can be equivocal. Since driving is a repetitive task, the findings in this study can be useful to this paper.

The Value of Music The Effects of Music in the Workplace: A Review of the Psychological Evidence by Dr Adrian C. North concludes that when the right kind of a music is chosen it enhances various aspects of life significantly. Choosing the correct style, tempo and volume of music affects task performance, physical labour, morale, health and social behaviour positively. This study by Dr Adrian C. North demonstrates that repetitive, mundane or undemanding tasks will generate a better level of performance if fast music is played to the workers. At the cheque clearing centre 72 workers were played fast, slow, and no music, over three weeks. Fast music led to 12.5% more cheques being cleared than did no music and to 22.3% more cheques being cleared than did slow music. This shows that fast music aids performance of tasks as it increases the arousal levels of the workers.

The Sound of Productivity Analysing Attitudes Towards Music Listening in the Workplace by Dr. Anneli Haake and Deezer

In this particular study the researchers have found out that 79% of the respondents would benefit from listening to music in workplace regardless of their age, occupation, location and personal taste or habits. Especially millennial and Gen Z workers prefer music to perform tasks compared to people born in the 1950s. There are certain industries where the employees are not allowed to listen to music and certain industries where music listening is encouraged. Insurance, Banking, Accountancy and Customer service are the least music-friendly industries and Computer programming, Data analytics, Advertising and Marketing are the most music-friendly industries. Music can be a distraction but helps focus. It can distract one from the external as well as internal noise. In this study there were only 4% respondents said that they don’t listen to music at all.

The Effect of Background Music and Background Noise on the Task Performance of Introverts and Extraverts Study by Gianna Cassidy and Raymond A.R. Macdonald

In this study immediate recall, free recall, numerical and delayed recall, and Stroop are the five cognitive tasks that has been used to see what effect music has on the listeners. As it turns out performance on all tasks was poorer while listening to background sound (music and noise) compared to completing the tasks in silence, supporting literature on the negative effects of background noise and music on task performance (Banbury and Berry, 1998). The results support Konecni’s (1982) suggestion that music processing takes up cognitive capacity and hence could be impact negatively on the tasks that involve intense focus.

The Impact of Music on Task Performance at Work by Courtney Wilson

In this study the researcher has considered all possible variables in music such as structure of the music, tempo, mode, rhythm and complexity. And there is a clear relationship between all the above mentioned variables and task performance. According to this study more complex the structure of the song the lower the performance of the task. Similarly as the complexity of the task reduces the performance increases and vice versa.

Research Methodology

This descriptive study is based on a secondary data that has been collected from various sources. There has been plenty of research on this particular area and has helped the employers to understand how exactly music can bring a positive change in employees’ behaviour.

Findings

1. Music does serve as a motivation to employees who are music lovers. The study conducted by Dr Anneli Haake and Deezer in the paper titled The sound of productivity Analysing attitudes towards music listening in the workplace shows the evidence.
2. Music helps to avoid boredom and hence increase that rate at which repetitive tasks are performed as proved by Dr Adrian C. North in his research titled The Value of Music The Effects of Music in the Workplace: A Review of the Psychological Evidence
3. The study by GIANNA CASSIDY AND RAYMOND A.R. MACDONALD in their research titled The effect of background music and background noise on the task performance of introverts and extraverts has proven that cognitive tasks involving focus requires more silence than background music.
4. Its only when the employees are given freedom to choose the music they like can this whole process of music and productivity can have a positive outcome. Music which is imposed on employees may prove to be counter- productive.
5. The Impact of Music on Task Performance at Work by Courtney Wilson has advocated that complex music does not do any favours to the employees as the music itself takes up cognitive space and it might interfere with the work performance.
6. With the tasks requiring team work, employers need to ensure all the group members are familiar with music that is played which eventually leads to team members getting along well.
7. Employees tend to be more open minded when they are happy. So choosing a happy song to play in the workplace will lead to increased co operation among team members.

Discussion

This study is important because of the omnipresence of music and its usage in almost every aspect of life. A human brain can move mountains, if the free will is utilized well. But the brain

can only unleash its greatness if it is exposed to a right environment and stimuli. One does not need research to understand that music make certain tasks such as driving or running enjoyable. The purpose of this study is to find out whether there can be any economic benefit to listening to music. Variables such as tempo, rhythm, mode, structure and complexity can only help us understand its effect on human behaviour more. There needs to be more research on whether music can be applied to all sectors or all industries. Because different roles of the job requires different skill sets and whether music can bring a positive change to all skills sets is still a question.

Limitations

1. This study has not been generalized to all sectors.
2. Only running or driving is considered for repetitive tasks.
3. It is assumed that any task which has become a muscle memory does not require too much focus
4. It is assumed that majority of the people do like music
5. As the organisations advance with respect to technology, systems and structure this area of study requires more research.

Conclusion

Music playing at work place has an implication on the employers. If they are not carefully choosing the type of music to suit the type of task the employees has to perform it can negate the positive effects of the whole process of playing music. Ultimately the technological advancement can be used to one’s advantage to a greater extend as it gives freedom for an employee to chose music which suits his/her tastes. As discussed in the paper music is all pervading and appeals to majority of the people and here is a chance for employers to strategize it accordingly. Whether the music should be allowed in all sectors is still up for debate. The tasks involving interdependence of groups may need more research especially considering the heterogeneous nature of the people within the same groups.

References

1. <https://qz.com/work/1573440/why-music-affects-your-productivity/> accessed on 26th June 2019.
2. <https://medium.com/@melissachu/5-types-of-music-that-increase-your-productivity-according-to-science-6214d5a5fe3f> accessed on 26th June 2019.
3. THIS IS YOUR BRAIN ON MUSIC the author Daniel Levitin Dutton Penguin publishers Pg No. 236.
4. Music and Emotions in the Brain: Familiarity Matters Carlos Silva Pereira, JoãoTeixeira, Patrícia Figueiredo, João Xavier, São Luís Castro, Elvira Brattico Published: November 16, 2011<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0027241>.
5. Music affects both introverts and extroverts differently study published in the Applied Cognitive Psychology Journal Article in Applied Cognitive Psychology 25(2):307 - 313 • March 2011
6. E. GLENN SCHELLENBERG in his paper Exposure to music and cognitive performance: tests of children and adults. Psychology of Music 35(1):5-19 • January 2007 DOI: 10.1177/0305735607068885.
7. Effects of noise and music on human and task performance: A systematic review by Brian H. Dalton and David G. Behm Occupational Ergonomics 7(3):143-152 • January 2007
8. The Value of Music The Effects of Music in the Workplace: A Review of the Psychological Evidence by Dr Adrian C. North May 2004.

9. The sound of productivity Analysing attitudes towards music listening in the workplace by Dr Anneli Haake and Deezer <https://www.musictank.co.uk/resources/industry-insight/the-sound-of-productivity-analysing-attitudes-towards-music-listening-in-the-workplace/> (Accessed on 4th November 2019).
10. The effect of background music and background noise on the task performance of introverts and extraverts study by GIANNA CASSIDY AND RAYMOND A.R. MACDONALD First Published July 1, 2007 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735607076444>.
11. Wilson, Courtney, “The Impact of Music on Task Performance at Work” (2018). Accounting Undergraduate Honors Theses. 28. <http://scholarworks.uark.edu/acctuht/28>.